

Smelting Reduction of Bauxite Residue and Beneficiation By-product in View of a Leachable Slag and Pig Iron Production

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Abstract

During the production of alumina with the commercial Bayer process, Bauxite Residue (red mud) is produced, which is one of the largest industrial waste streams currently, in alumina production. A more sustainable way for the production of alumina from bauxite without Bauxite Residue (BR) production is the Pedersen Process, which also enables the use a wider range of bauxite qualities, in terms of silica and iron. This process, is a combined pyrometallurgical-hydrometallurgical process. In this study, two waste materials from the bauxite mineral processing and alumina industry are treated to produce pig iron and a feedstock for alumina production. The scope of the present work is to study the possibility of using the above raw materials in the Pedersen Process, for the utilization of BR. Industrially produced Bauxite Residue (BR) and a calcium-carbonate rich bauxite mineral beneficiation by-product are milled and then mixed in different portions with lime. These mixtures are smelted at elevated temperatures and the iron oxide is reduced by carbon. This yields separable pig iron and calcium-aluminate slag products. The slag and metal produced are thoroughly analyzed. It is shown that the main slag phases, their amounts and distribution in the produced slags are different for different utilized mixtures. Moreover, it is also shown that the produced slags are promising for further application of the method to utilize the industrial waste and byproduct.

Introduction

Bauxite is the primary raw material for the alumina production. It is treated through a hydrometallurgical process, called Bayer Process, where sodium hydroxide (NaOH) is used for its digestion. During this process a byproduct is formed, known as Bauxite Residue (BR) in literature. Iron and other impurities that are insoluble in caustic solutions comprise the main components of BR. These components are removed by clarification step as shown in Figure 1 [1]. The recent years, increase in alumina production caused a massive production of BR. One ton of alumina production can generate between 0.8 to 1.5 tons of BR [2, 3]. The disposal of BR remains a major problem due to its high volume and high alkalinity. It is presenting not economically consumable and causes environmental problems due to its characteristics. The utilization of BR is still unsolved even if it can be used in the fields of building, pollution control, metal recovery (iron, titanium, aluminum, alkali, rare earth elements), coagulant, adsorbent, catalyst and in soil remediation.

The presence of valuable elements such as iron (Fe), titanium (Ti), aluminum (Al), scandium (Sc) and REEs [4] makes the BR a quite interesting secondary raw material. Iron as oxides / hydroxides is usually the main component in BR. There are different approaches for iron separation such as:

- a) solid-state reduction of iron from BR followed by magnetic separation to recover iron,
- b) reduction smelting in a blast / electric or other type furnace to produce pig iron
- c) leaching extraction method [5, 6].

Aluminum oxide / hydroxide in BR is also relatively high, ranging from 15 % to 30 % [7], showing the direct loss of alumina in the Bayer process.

In this paper, the main focus is to investigate the possibility to use BR and CaCO₃-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product as raw materials for the production of a slag that can be a feedstock for alumina production and a valuable pig iron. This might contribute to reducing the environmental challenges caused by BR disposal.

Figure 1: Simplified alumina production method by Bayer Process [7]

Harald Pedersen patented in 1920s a different process for the production of Alumina (Figure 2) from bauxite, which was commercialized until 1969 in Norway [7]. The first step of the process is to smelt and reduce bauxite with CaO as flux and coke as a reduction agent [8]. The iron oxide is reduced to molten iron and can be separated easily due to higher density than the molten slag. The produced pig iron can further be used in the ferrous industry. The second product of this step is a calcium- aluminate slag that is further hydrometallurgically treated for the recovery of Al. The non-soluble residue, called grey mud contains significant amount of calcium carbonate and can be used in the other industry [7] as well as for REEs extraction [9].

Even if BR cannot become a competitive raw material for iron and steel making due to its low concentration in iron (30 – 50%) compared to the commercial iron concentrates (> 90 %). The scarcity of available raw materials and the need for sustainable industrial operations underline the need for the

development of new approaches based on secondary resources with almost zero-waste production [3]. The scope of this work is to study the feasibility of applying the pyrometallurgical part of Pedersen process. The main focus is the smelting reduction of BR and the CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product for the production of pig iron as well as for making a leachable slag for further hydrometallurgical treatment. Obviously, the simultaneous production of the two valuable products may outline a process for the utilization of the BR.

The common argues for not using this method industrially, are on the one hand due to the lack of literature and scientific evidence for the pyrometallurgical part [10]. On the other hand, it is believed that this method cannot be a sustainable approach or compete with Bayer Process. After all, according to the results, this process may be a sustainable approach for the alumina production and it is worthwhile to study and solve some of the old problems that the Pedersen Process have.

Figure 2: Simplified alumina production method from bauxite by the Pedersen Process [7]

Experimental Procedure and calculations

The experimental work flow of the present study is schematically shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: An illustration of the experimental work in this study.

An Ellingham diagram for the basic thermodynamic analysis of the system was calculated by using the HSC Chemistry 9.2, which is a commercial chemistry software.

Materials Preparation and Characterization

A commercial Bauxite Residue and a CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation byproduct were provided by Aluminium of Greece (AoG) as the starting materials. The materials were first homogenized and then representative samples from the two materials were dried in a furnace at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. Furthermore, lime used as a flux. The chemical analysis of the major elements of the three materials was determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF). Structural analysis of the raw materials were performed by X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) using a Bruker D-8 Focus analyzer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation, 10 to 75 deg diffraction angle, 0.01 deg step size, and 2.5 deg for both primary and secondary soler slits.

The raw materials were calcined at $850\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h in a muffle furnace in air to remove the chemical and crystalline water in the hydroxides. Two different mixtures of the calcined raw materials were prepared to study the effect of composition in the produced slags. The mixture I contains 40 % CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product and 60 % BR. The mixture II, contains 20 % CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product and 80 % BR. An addition of 21 % and 16 % of lime was added to the mixtures, respectively and put into open graphite crucibles with inner diameter of 32 mm and 95 mm height.

The chemical analyses for the produced slag was performed by (ICP-MS), while the structural analyses was performed by XRD. To study the microstructure of the slags, scanning electron microscope (SEM) supported by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis were applied.

Smelting-reduction trials

The crucibles containing the materials mixtures was placed in a 75-kVA induction furnace and heated slowly with the rate of 27.5 °C/min until it reached 1650 °C. We can consider an oxidizing atmosphere during the smelting reduction process over the crucibles, because of the open furnace operation [10]. The duration of the smelting reduction was 30 min and the produced slag and metal in the crucibles were cooled down to the room temperature inside the furnace, slow cooling rate, around 25 °C/min. According to the literature [11] rapid cooling rate gives a glassy slag, and the applied cooling rate may yield crystalline slags. The slow cooling rate improves the further leachability of the slags as well [12,13]. To measure the temperature during the treatment, a tungsten / rhenium thermocouple (type C) located inside a graphite thermowell, and an encapsulating alumina insulation tube was used to prevent the direct contact of graphite with the thermocouple tip. For further analysis, the solidified materials and the crucible were crushed to separate slag and metal from the crucible.

The CaO to Al₂O₃ ratio is an important part of the procedure for the formation of the most leachable calcium aluminate phases as described in literature [11, 14]. Based on the previous study at NTNU, the most leachable calcium-aluminate species in the slags can be ordered as CaO • Al₂O₃, 3CaO • Al₂O₃ and CaO • 2Al₂O₃, respectively [14]. In this study the CaO/Al₂O₃ ratio was fixed in the range of 1 – 2 % in the final slags.

The reduction of iron oxide occurs by the graphite crucible at elevated temperatures and so no additional coke was used as the previous work [14].

Results and Discussion

Characteristics of the materials

The chemical analysis of the CaCO₃-rich bauxite beneficiation byproduct (Table 1) indicates the high calcium content of the material, and is much higher than that in BR. The concentration of Al₂O₃ in the both materials is high, while there is significant higher amount of iron in the BR than in the CaCO₃-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product. Titanium and silicon are higher in BR due to the clarification step of Bayer process that separate the insoluble residue (BR) from the pregnant solution [15,16]. Sodium is higher in BR as well, due to the formation of DSP (‘desilication product’), sodalite and cancrinite, during the Bayer Process [16, 17].

Table 1: XRF analysis of the CaCO₃-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product, BR and lime.

Oxides	CaCO ₃ -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product	Bauxite Residue	Lime (CaO)
	wt.-%	wt.- %	wt.-%
Al ₂ O ₃	30.95	24.6	0.24
CaO	57.24*	9.39	97.2*
Fe ₂ O ₃	8.62	47.2	0.083
TiO ₂	1.55	6.68	0.015
SiO ₂	1.22	7.7	0.46
K ₂ O	-	0.08	0.04
MgO	0.2	0.2	0.64
Na ₂ O	-	3.10	0.116
MnO	0.04	0.04	0.006
P ₂ O ₅	-	0.03	0.022
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.09	0.33	-
ZrO ₂	-	0.2	-
NiO	0.012	0.15	-
Sc ₂ O ₃	-	0.015	-

*as CaCO₃*1.7 wt.-% as CaCO₃

The XRD (Fig. 4) and XRF (Table 1) analysis of BR indicate that the Al extraction from Bauxite is insufficient due to the high remaining Al content in BR, 24,6 %. The Fig. 4 reveals that the predominance phase of BR is hematite (H). Aluminum is mostly present as gibbsite (G), to lower extent as bohemite (B) and traces as diaspore (D). High amount of aluminum are bonded in Sodium Aluminum Silicate (SAS), sodalite and Cancrinite (Cn). Titanium appears as Anatase (A).

Figure 4: XRD analysis of Bauxite Residue

The XRD pattern of CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation byproduct confirms the XRF analysis as about the high calcium content. The calcite (CaCO_3) is the predominance phase. Furthermore the aluminum is mostly present as Diaspore (D), to lower extend as bohemite (B) and some traces of Sodium Aluminum Silicate (S).

Figure 5: XRD analysis of CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product.

The mass losses after the thermal treatment (calcination) are given in Table 2. The decomposition of CaCO_3 happens above $890\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, as we can see on the lower weight loss of CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product that mainly consist of CaCO_3 (Fig 5). This implies that higher temperature or longer duration are required for the complete transformation of calcite to CaO and CO_2 .

Table 2: Mass losses of BR and CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product in the high temperature calcination step.

Raw Material	Mass before calcination (g)	Mass after calcination (g)	Total weight loss (%)
BR	79.41	54.86	30.9
CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation byproduct	46.4	39.22	15.5

As mentioned in previous section the mixture I has higher amount of Al_2O_3 and CaO due to the higher amount of CaCO_3 -rich bauxite beneficiation by-product, as shown in Table 3. The concentration of iron, titanium, silicon and sodium in mixture II are higher due to the higher BR content.

Table 3: Averaged composition of the mixture I (40 % bauxite beneficiation by-product, 60 % BR and 21 % lime) and mixture II (20 % bauxite beneficiation by-product, 80 % BR and 16 % lime)

Oxides (%)	wt.-% composition of the mixtures	
	Mixture I	Mixture II
Al_2O_3	21.6	22
Fe_2O_3	25.34	33.52
SiO_2	4.28	5.62
TiO_2	3.69	4.8
CaO	43.18	31.58
Na_2O	1.51	2.13
Cr_2O_3	0.17	0.24
MgO	0.14	0.1
S	0.08	0.06

Smelting-reduction

The reduction of Fe_2O_3 to metallic iron is possible by carbon (the crucible wall) which causes CO generation. As described in literature [18] the Na_2O can be reduced by carbon at temperatures lower than $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Carbon can reduce SiO_2 at around $1650\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and TiO_2 at above $1700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. While Al_2O_3 and CaO cannot be reduced at temperatures lower than $2000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Taking into account the melting point of iron, $1537\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the operation temperature for this test is set to $1650\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in order to effectively

reduce iron from BR [18]. It is worth mentioning that as the produced iron is getting saturated in carbon due to the contact with graphite crucible, it will have lower melting point than pure iron. The whole mechanism is described in Ellingham Diagram (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Ellingham Diagram for the oxidation of some metals, calculated by HSC Chemistry 9.2

Characteristics of the slags

The ICP-MS analysis of the produced slags, Table 4, shows that the $\text{CaO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio is 1.77 and 1.22 for the mixture I and II, respectively. For the both cases the produced slags are enriched in Al and Ca content in comparison with the starting materials. The low content of Na indicate our first assumption about the evaporation as $\text{Na}(\text{g})$ during the high temperature smelting-reduction process regarding Figure 6. The remaining iron in slags is due to the entrap of metallic iron in the slags matrix (confirmed by microscopic work), and the low Fe content indicates the good separation of metal and slag as well the high iron recoveries. The XRD and SEM analysis confirm the Ti content that will be described below.

Table 4: Chemical Analysis of the produced slag I (40 % bauxite beneficiation by-product, 60 % BR and 21 % lime) and II (20 % bauxite beneficiation by-product, 80 % BR and 16 % lime) measured by ICP-MS.

Oxides	wt.-% composition of slags	
	Slag I	Slag II
Al ₂ O ₃	31.19	36.86
CaO	55.08	44
SiO ₂	5.67	8.49
Na ₂ O	0.0034	0.01
MnO	0.06	0.07
MgO	0.16	0.16
K ₂ O	0.0030	0.0024
TiO ₂	4.85	7.2
V ₂ O ₅	0.1	0.1
P ₂ O ₅	0.08	0.06
NiO	0.0025	0.0026
Sc ₂ O ₃	0.01	0.01
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.1	0.1
Fe content	2.69	2.94

The phase identification of the produced slags by XRD analysis are shown in Figures 7 and 8. In slag I, the aluminum is mostly present as tricalcium aluminium oxide ($3 \text{ CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) [4], mayenite ($12 \text{ CaO} \cdot 7 \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3$) (2) and calcium aluminum silicate [3]. Perovskite (CaTiO_3) [1] is the main phase that contains titanium. The slag II consists many different phases due to the higher BR content. Most abundant seems to be the Calcium Aluminum Silicate [3], Mayenite [2] and Perovskite (CaTiO_3) [1] and also tri-calcium aluminum oxide ($3 \text{ CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) [4] appears at 2theta values 22.3° , 33.2° , 47.7° , and 59.3° as Tam Wai Yin et al observed as well [19]. The main peaks of mayenite and calcium aluminum silicate overlap, making it difficult to quantify them.

Figure 7: XRD spectrum of slag I and the characterized peaks.

From the XRD analysis of the two slags, the titania transforms completely to perovskite (CaTiO_3) that according to Kauben et al, may affect positively the alumina extraction [20].

Figure 8: XRD spectrum of slag II and the characterized peaks.

The high amount of calcium titanate in the slags can be confirmed with SEM / EDS analysis in both cases (Figure 9 a and 10 a). However, in the slag I the CaTiO_3 present in large amounts in irregular shape and distributed between CA (calcium-aluminate) and CAS (calcium aluminate silicate) phases (Figure 9 a). While in slag II it is close to the boundaries of CA and CAS particles and is observed in dendritic form (Figure 10 a).

Figure 9: SEM analysis of (a) slag I (40 % bauxite beneficiation by-product, 60 % BR and 21 % lime) with major phases calcium aluminate (CA), Calcium aluminate silicate (CAS), Calcium titanate (CT), Calcium silicate (CS) and (b) the corresponding metallic phase. Graphite flakes (C), metallic iron (Fe).

It is worth noting that the chemical compositions of the produced metals, metal matrices, were similar with around 95 %Fe and 5 % impurities that are mostly C, Si in lower amount and traces of Ti.

Figure 10: SEM analysis of (a) slag II (20 % bauxite beneficiation by-product, 80 % BR and 16 % lime) and (b) the corresponding metallic phase with the major phases calcium aluminate (CA), calcium aluminosilicate (CAS), calcium titanate (CT), graphite flakes (C), metallic iron (Fe) and intermetallic phase (*).

The slag II seems to have a more complex morphology, where the CA phases is present as needle structure in 2D images, which are expected to be thick plates in 3D. The metallic phase in both cases has similar microstructure (Figure 9b and 10b) in which graphite flakes are distributed in a metallic matrix. In metal II (Figure 10b) there are some intermetallic phases consisted of Ti, Fe, V, Nb and C, which are most likely complex carbides and are most likely precipitated during the solidification and cooling as described previously [21].

Conclusion

The smelting and carbothermic reduction of mixtures of BR and a CaCO₃-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product was done and the products were characterized. The main results can be summarized as follows.

1. The smelting-reduction of mixtures yields slags containing leachable calcium aluminate phases, and their amount is depending on the mixture composition.
2. Al in the produced slags is mainly in calcium aluminate phases, and calcium silicate aluminate phases. Higher portion of BR content causes the formation of more calcium aluminate silicate phase, which are less leachable.
3. The lime in the mixtures and its reaction with titania upon solidification forms perovskite (CaTiO₃) which is more thermodynamically stable phase and may affect the alumina extraction.
4. The low content of iron in the produced slags indicate high iron recoveries, above 95%.
5. Proper separation of metal and slag occurs in the smelting-reduction step, however, some tiny metallic particles were entrapped in the slag phase.
6. According to the above results, the possibility to use BR and CaCO₃-rich bauxite beneficiation by product as raw materials in the Pedersen Process, for the recovery of alumina and iron, seems to be promising for the utilization of BR.

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